

THE INFLUENCE OF HOME FACTORS ON MATHEMATICS OUTCOMES IN MULTIGRADE CLASSROOMS

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Multigrade classrooms are a significant feature of the Irish educational landscape in primary schools, particularly in rural settings. Conflicting results are reported from studies analysing academic achievements of students in multigrade classrooms. While it is widely reported that students in single-grade and multigrade classes achieve similar results in academic achievement tests, recent research has suggested that this is not true in all situations. It has been noted that longitudinal studies have revealed unstable outcomes in student achievement. The aim of this study is to explore the academic outcomes for children in multigrade settings in small schools in Ireland drawing on data from two waves of the 'Growing Up in Ireland' (GUI) study. In 2007, the first wave involved a nationally representative sample of 8568 nine-year old children, 1,250 of whom were being educated in multigrade classrooms in small schools. Four years later, over 1100 of these multigrade children participated in the second wave of the study. In this paper, measures of mathematics norm-referenced tests undertaken by the children at age 9 and age 13 are analysed. In addition, home factors are also explored. The outcomes for children in multigrade classes in small schools are compared with their single-grade counterparts. The data provide significant insight into the academic achievements of the students involved in the study as well as home factors which influence their achievement.

INTRODUCTION

Multigrade education is a form of education which receives little acknowledgement in educational policy, research or curricula to the point which it is sometimes considered 'invisible' (Little, 2001). In multigrade classes, students from two or more separate grades are taught in the same setting (Quail & Smyth, 2014). Just under 30% of primary-school children in Ireland are taught in multigrade classes (Eivers & Chubb, 2017). There has been little research on the impact of multigrade classes on student outcomes, particularly which considers the influences of home factors such on student attainment (Fan & Chen, 1999).

This study is focused on children's mathematics attainment in multigrade classes in small schools and aims to offer a perspective on the role of home-factors. It sets out to establish if children in multigrade classes in small schools have similar levels of attainment to their single-grade counterparts. Secondly, it aims to advance research on student achievement by considering aspects of children's backgrounds such as family characteristics and parental involvement in their children's education as partial explanations for influences on attainment. Thirdly, we aim to explore if the influence of background factors on achievement varies according to the age of the child.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Impact of multigrade classes on student mathematics outcomes: International studies

Research investigating mathematics outcomes for students in multigrade classes compare test results of these students against results of students of a similar age in a single grade class. In the majority of studies, the test instrument is a standardized achievement test. Studies of

mathematics outcomes for children in multigrade classes reach a diverse range of conclusions. Adams (1953) examined the arithmetic reasoning and arithmetic fundamentals of fifth grade students in multigrade and combination classes with fourth grade students. Adams concluded that children were not held back by being grouped with students in a lower grade level. Two decades later, a study by Veenman (1995) provided support for the findings of Adams (1953). This synthesis of previous studies examining student outcomes in multigrade and multiage classes reported that the multigrade classes are simply no worse and no better than single grade classes (Veenman, 1995). Indeed, a more recent study by Thomas (2012) converges on the same findings as those by Adams and Veenman.

However, a number of studies challenge the findings of these studies. A year after his 1995 study, Veenman (1996) reconsidered his conclusions and stated that upon further analysis there was some support for the possibility that student achievement in mathematics may suffer in multigrade classes. Similarly, Russell, Rowe and Hill (1998) reported that their examination of mathematics assessments results suggested that being educated in a multigrade class had a negative, albeit non-significant, effect on student mathematics outcomes. Mariano and Kirby (2009) concluded that overall, 3rd, 4th and 5th grade students in multigrade classrooms experienced consistently small and negative effects and achieved lower scores than expected had they been in a monograde classroom, even when teacher characteristics were taken into account. For most of the students involved in the study, being in a multigrade classroom appeared to have a statistically significant effect, with the exception of 4th graders who were in a combined multigrade with 5th grade pupils.

Impact of multigrade classes on student mathematics outcomes: Irish studies

The National Assessments of Mathematics and English Reading (NAMER) carried out by the Educational Research Centre since 1972 offer insights into student attainment in Ireland. Eivers, Close, Shiel, Millar, Clerkin, Gilleece and Kiniry (2010) found no significant difference between the achievement levels of students in single-grade and multigrade schools in mathematics in NAMER 2009. Although both second class and sixth class pupils in multigrade classes achieved a higher mean score than their single-grade counterparts, the differences were not statistically significant (Eivers et al, 2010).

An analysis of the mathematics scores of nine-year old Irish students in a separate study carried out by Quail and Smyth (2014), using the norm-referenced Drumcondra Mathematics achievement test, similarly concluded that being in a multigrade class had little impact. However, when the outcomes were disaggregated according to gender, girls in classes with older children scored significantly worse in maths than those in single-grade classes.

Factors influencing outcomes

Some studies extend beyond comparison of mathematics achievement scores and focus on identifying factors which may influence outcomes. While Thomas (2012) examined variables such as the influence of prior academic achievement on future outcomes, he also acknowledged that one potential variable omitted from his analyses was parental involvement. The selection of background characteristics in our study is informed by the pertinent literature and focuses predominantly on the relationship between parental involvement and academic outcomes.

Parental factors and student educational attainment

The relationship between *parental employment* and children's educational attainment has been explored in a several studies (Ermisch & Francesconi, 2002). According to Schildberg-Horisch (2016), the effect of parental employment status on educational achievement is not obvious as parental employment reduces the time available to parents to spend with their child, while simultaneously increasing the availability of resources within the family. *Socio-economic status* is a relevant factor at the individual level (Capraro, Capraro & Wiggins, 2000). Coleman (1968) claimed that socio-economic factors bear a strong relation to academic achievement, to the point that differences between schools account for only a small fraction of student achievement. *The level of parents' education* is an important influence in the achievement of their children (Smyth, Whelan, McCoy, Quail & Doyle, 2009). The involvement and *engagement of parents* with schools, particularly where parents support learning in the home has been noted as bring a significant influence in raising achievement (Harris & Goodall, 2007). Studies have also examined *parental expectations* and found associations between parents' educational expectations and children's attainment (Seginer, 1986). Studies have raised questions about the direction of the relationship between expectations and attainment (Spera, Wentzel & Matto, 2009). Finally, *family structure* is reported as being an influence in academic success (Ermishch & Francesconi, 2001). Although research frequently focuses on both family structure and marital status of parents, it is also acknowledged that the estimated effect of childhood family structure on achievement may be spurious (Mayer, 1997).

METHODOLOGY

This research involves secondary analysis of data collected from a national longitudinal study of children in Ireland called the 'Growing Up in Ireland' study. The 'Growing Up in Ireland' (GUI) study is funded by the Irish government and is being undertaken in a joint collaboration between the Economic and Social Research Institute and Trinity College Dublin (ESRI, 2010). In 2007, data collection commenced on a nationally representative sample of 8568 nine- year- old children. In excess of 2700 of children were in multigrade classes at age 9. Of these, 1253 attended small schools where all children would generally expect to spend the duration of their primary schooling in multigrade classes. This paper reports on the analysis of data supplied by the children and parents in their questionnaires, along with academic outcomes in mathematics at two time points (ages 9 and 13). The academic outcomes data reported in this study are gleaned from results on norm-referenced mathematics assessments (Drumcondra Numerical Ability test) administered as part of the study. The study uses descriptive and inferential statistics to analyse the data including regression models.

Data collection and analysis

The outcome variable, mathematics achievement logit score, is measured at two time-points: age 9 and age 13. The logit score is used in this study as it takes account of variations in the level of difficulty in the test questions, as well as adjusting the results according to the grade level of the child. The home factors explored in this study were (i) the employment status of

the primary caregiver, (ii) the highest level of education achieved by the primary caregiver, (iii) social class, (iv) parental involvement, (v) parental expectations and (vi) family structure.

Both descriptive and inferential analyses are carried out on the GUI data. The distributions of mathematics scores achieved by children in multigrade classes in small schools are compared with their single-grade counterparts. Independent samples t-tests investigate if differences in mean scores for both groups are significant at $p=.05$ level. In order to explore the impact of home factors on mathematics outcomes for children, family and parental measures are included in a regression model. Although multiple regression can predict the value of the outcome variable, in this study the multiple regression determines the proportion of the variation in mathematics achievement explained by the background factors.

FINDINGS

First, we investigate the mathematics outcomes from wave 1 of the GUI study for 9-year old children in small multigrade classes ($n=1248$) and compare them to their peers in single-grade classes ($n=5114$). Analysis of the logit score indicates that while there were small differences in the mean scores, in favour of those children in multigrade classrooms, they were not significantly different. Figure 1 illustrates the distribution of mathematics logit scores. For the students in multigrade classes, there was a smaller range of scores, with the minimum score in a multigrade class being -3.1 and the maximum score being 1.9 . In single-grade classes, while the maximum score was the same, the minimum score was lower at -3.62 . The mean scores for both group were similar (multigrade mean = $-.779$; single-grade mean = $-.726$). This is not a statistically significant difference ($t=-1.793$, $p=.073$).

Figure 1: Comparison of logit scores for children in multigrade and single-grade classes at age 9

Our second analysis investigates the mathematics outcomes from wave 2 of the GUI study. Wave 2 focused on the same children (as in Wave 1) when they progressed in their education to age 13. Figure 2 reveals differences in mathematics outcomes between children who are likely to have been in multigrade classes for the duration of primary school ($n=1177$) and those in single-grade classes ($n=4247$). Again, we see that the mean logit score for children in multigrade classes was slightly higher. This difference of $.06064$, although small, was statistically significant indicating that among students at age 13, children from multigrade classes performed better than those in single-grade classes ($t=1.982$, $p<.05$).

Figure 2: Distribution of logit scores for children in multigrade and single- grade classes at age 13

Home factors influencing mathematics achievement: Descriptive Statistics

The specific home factors were gleaned from questionnaires completed by parents. The questionnaire required the primary and secondary caregiver to identify their employment status, family structure and occupation which was used to determine social class. In addition they responded to a series of questions. Three questions provide relevant data in this study: What is the highest level of education (full-time or part-time) which you have completed? How often do you/your spouse provide help with homework? How far do you expect study child to go in education/training?

Table 1 presents the descriptive data for parental expectations at ages 9 and 13 and shows the highest level of education they expect their children to attain. Table 2 presents the descriptive data for five home factors: employment status, family type, level of education for the primary caregiver social class (as measured by parental occupation), and frequency of homework help. Table 2 presents the descriptive data for parental expectations at ages 9 and 13. As can be seen from analysis of tables 1-2, the employment status of the primary caregivers of both groups of children are very similar. A smaller proportion of children in multigrade classes come from households with a single adult. A greater proportion of parents of students in single-grade classes have achieved a degree or post-graduate qualification. A larger proportion of parents of children in single-grade classes expect their children to attain post-graduate degrees or higher degrees. Parents of children in multigrade classes also appeared to help with homework more frequently. Regarding social class, twice as many parents of children in single-grade classes are in professional social class and a greater proportion of parents of children in multigrade classes being in skilled or semi-skilled manual labour.

Table 1: Parents’ expectations for their children at ages 9 and 13

	Multigrade		Single-grade	
	Age 9	Age 13	Age 9	Age 13
Junior Certificate or Equivalent	0.4%	0.3%	0.8%	0.4%
Leaving Certificate/ Equivalent	12.4%	5.3%	10.5%	7.0%
An apprenticeship or trade	10.7%	5.9%	5.3%	3.8%
Diploma or Certificate	12.7%	9.4%	10.2%	9.1%
Degree	45.5%	53.4%	50.3%	47.3%
Postgraduate/higher degree	18.2%	23.8%	23.0%	30.7%
Don’t know (option at age 13)		2.1%		1.6%

Table 2: Home factor variables

	Multigrade	Single Grade
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Employment Status		
Work or in training	58%	59.9%
Home duties or retired	35.7%	32.8%
In education	1.6%	1.6%
Unemployed	3.1%	3.5%
Family structure		
Single person and one or two children	7.2%	12.9%
Single person and three or more children	4.5%	7.1%
Couple and one or two children	32.6%	35.5%
Couple and three or more children	55.36%	44.5%
Level of education – primary caregiver		
No education or a primary education	4.7%	6.6%
Secondary or vocational	41.2%	35.3%
Degree or post-graduate	14.5%	18.9%
Family Social Class		
Professional workers	6.8%	12.7%
Managerial and technical	33.7%	36.2%
Non-manual	19.8%	18.4%
Skilled manual	17%	13.1%
Semi-skilled	13.8%	8.7%
Unskilled	1.4%	1.6%
Validly no social class	7.4%	9%
Frequency of homework help		
Always/Nearly Always	54.2%	50.3%
Regularly	21.0%	19.5%
Now and again	17.0%	18.5%
Rarely	6.1%	8.8%
Never	1.8%	3.0%

Table 3: R² value explaining the proportion of variance explained by parental factors at age 9

	Multigrade	Single-grade
Employment status of primary caregiver	.025	.001
Family structure	.037	.011
Primary caregiver's highest level of education	.071	.057
Secondary caregiver's highest level of education	.093	.076
Family's social class	.093	.078
Parent's expectations	.122	.133
Parental involvement with homework	.144	.157

A multiple linear regression model incorporating these background factors was constructed to investigate their influence on mathematics outcomes at age 9. Among 9 year old children in small schools (Table 3), the model accounted for 14.4% in the variation in students' mathematics outcomes. There is a statistically significant result $F(6, 1095) = 21.528$, $p < .0005$. The same factors accounted for 15.7% of the variation in mathematics outcomes among children in single-grade classes. Similarly, the regression model indicates a statistically significant result $F(6, 4378) = 114.371$, $p < .0005$.

Table 4: R² value explaining the proportion of variance explained by parental factors at age 13

	Multigrade	Single grade
Employment status of primary caregiver	.016	.004
Family structure	.035	.011
Primary caregiver's highest level of education	.078	.083
Secondary caregiver's highest level of education	.087	.106
Family's social class	.087	.107
Parent's expectations	.117	.179
Parental involvement with homework	.132	.201

At age 13, parental factors continued to explain variance in mathematics attainment. The proportion of variance explained by home factors decreased to 13.2% among students in small schools, but increased to 20.1% for their single-grade counterparts (Table 4).

At age 9, the mathematics attainment of children in multigrade classes and children in single-grade classes was similar. At age 13, children who previously studied in a multigrade class achieved higher scores than their single-grade counterparts. Multiple factors influence academic achievement outcomes. In this study, parental characteristics, involvement and expectations explain a proportion of variance in the mathematics scores of their children. The influence of home factors varies according to the classroom structure and the age of the child. It is interesting to note that while parents' expectations and mother's education play an increasing role in the attainment of children in single-grade classes as they get older, home factors explain a smaller proportion of variance in achievement among students in multigrade classes in small schools as they get older. This suggests that there are other influencing factors which are not captured in the design of this study.

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